

EXPLORING THE EFFICACY OF AI CHATGPT IN ENHANCING SPEAKING SKILL AT LYCEUMS**Kasimova M.***EFL teacher at "Temurbeklar maktabi"
military-academic lyceum***Abstract**

With advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and its increasing integration into educational technologies, there is a need to evaluate the specific impacts on language proficiency. This study examines the effectiveness of AI chatbots, particularly ChatGPT4, in improving speaking skills among students in an academic lyceum setting. It aims to provide empirical evidence on the potential of AI chatbots to enhance language education by making it more interactive, engaging, and efficient. Using qualitative methods, including detailed surveys and direct observation, the study explores how AI chatbots can serve as personalized learning assistants, offering tailored feedback and interactive communication exercises. Key findings indicate significant improvements in vocabulary acquisition and speaking confidence, though challenges such as connectivity issues and feedback effectiveness were noted.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence (AI), AI chatbots, AI Chat GPT, speaking proficiency, technology in language acquisition.

Introduction

In recent years, the integration of AI technology into language learning environments has shown promising results in enhancing students' language skills, particularly in speaking through authentic contextual learning. Authentic contexts, crucial for language acquisition, provide learners with real-life scenarios that engage and challenge them, enhancing their language skills in practical situations [1]. Traditional AI-powered chatbots have become key in promoting such learning, offering conversational practice in supportive and immersive settings [2]. However, the effectiveness of these AI tools among specific groups, such as Uzbek learners of English, has not been thoroughly investigated.

This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of AI chatbots, especially ChatGPT4, in enhancing the speaking skills of academic lyceum students. Unlike traditional methods that may not offer consistent interactive opportunities, AI chatbots provide extensive practice in speaking, immediate feedback, and personalized language learning experiences [3]. These features are particularly beneficial for academic lyceum students who require intensive preparation for standard examinations (IELTS, National CEFR) and value direct and immediate feedback to improve their language proficiency.

By exploring these areas, the study seeks to deepen our understanding of AI's potential in language learning and to identify effective strategies to enhance speaking skills among learners. The study focuses on the nuances of AI ChatGPT technologies for improving speaking, aiming to illustrate how such tools can be integrated effectively to support and enhance language learning outcomes. The research question is:

How effective are AI chatbots, specifically ChatGPT4, in enhancing the speaking skills of lyceum students?

Recent studies have shown that AI chatbots are playing an increasingly significant role in language ed-

ucation, with their use expanding across various educational settings. Employing chatbots to strengthen speaking skills can lead to noticeable improvements in fluency and vocabulary growth [3]. There are two types of chatbots based on how they work: text-based and voice-enabled. Voice-enabled chatbots have been suggested as a useful tool for learning and practicing second language (L2) speaking skills [3]. Additionally, L2 learners often prefer chatbots over human partners because they are afraid of making mistakes or seeming less capable when talking to humans [4].

With advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), Natural Language Processing (NLP), and Deep Learning, developers are now creating more sophisticated humanoid chatbots. While these chatbots don't claim to have comprehensive knowledge, they aim to mimic realistic human interactions [5]. According to Wu & Yu (2024), AI chatbots have a more significant impact on higher education students than on primary and secondary learners. Short interventions lead to better learning outcomes than longer ones, likely due to the novelty effect of AI chatbots, which tends to diminish over time [6]. To improve effectiveness, future designs should include human-like avatars, gamification, and emotional intelligence features.

A study by Han demonstrated that *Alexa*, a widely-used voice-enabled chatbot, can enhance students' speaking abilities by engaging them in conversational practice. This research found that chatbot-facilitated learning notably improved students' pronunciation and fluency in the language [7]. Additionally, feedback from post-experiment questionnaires revealed that integrating such technology increased students' enthusiasm and motivation for learning. The sentence needs a slight correction for grammatical accuracy. Similarly, along with *Alexa*, *Google Assistant* has also been shown to positively affect students' language skills. Research indicated that students experienced reduced embarrass-

ment and anxiety while practicing with chatbots. Moreover, chatbots have been found to support self-directed learning of foreign languages in environments where native speakers may be unavailable [4]; [7].

While general chatbots can be appealing, research has indicated that they might not be as effective for second language (L2) learners due to their inability to meet specific learning needs [4]. Consequently, when designing a chatbot for language learning, several factors need to be considered, including the potential for language learning, the suitability for learners, and the authenticity of the content [4]. The potential for language learning should encompass elements such as interactional modification and a focus on relevant tasks. The suitability for learners should evaluate aspects like language proficiency, age, learning styles, and individual traits. Finally, the authenticity criterion requires that the chatbot content's reflection of real-world tasks that learners are likely to face, enhancing the overall learning experience.

This study assessed the effectiveness of ChatGPT4 in enhancing speaking skills among academic lyceum students over a one-week period using

qualitative data. Thirty students, aged 16-17 with pre-intermediate English proficiency, participated using ChatGPT version 4. Participants' use of ChatGPT was monitored through screen recordings and twice-weekly interviews, capturing their interactions and reflections. Qualitative data, including screen photos, interviews and the survey (Appendix 1) with open-ended and multiple-choice questions, were analyzed to assess the chatbot's impact.

The post-survey questionnaires offered insights into students' experiences and perceptions. Most students (63.3%) utilized ChatGPT for vocabulary building and conversational practice (53.3%), followed by pronunciation guidance (43.3%) and grammar practice (23.3%) (Chart 1). Regarding their interest in learning speaking skills with ChatGPT compared to traditional methods the majority of students, 63%, find learning with ChatGPT more interesting. Conversely, 26.7% of the students find it less interesting. Additionally, 10% of the students feel that learning with ChatGPT is the same as traditional methods.

In what ways have you used ChatGPT for improving your speaking skills?

30 responses

Chart 1

How do you feel about learning speaking skills with ChatGPT compared to traditional ways?

30 responses

Chart 2

Despite the advantages, some challenges were identified. Internet connection problems often interrupted the flow of conversations, hindering consistent practice. Additionally, some students struggled with mispronunciations and frequent errors. Moreover, while ChatGPT provided immediate feedback, it was not always effective in correcting these issues, leading to frustration and repeated mistakes.

Daniel said, “*Sometimes ChatGPT doesn't understand me though.*”

Long pauses during interactions with ChatGPT also disrupted the natural rhythm of conversation, making practice sessions less engaging and effective. Not all students benefited equally from using ChatGPT. Some students who initially showed great interest did not see significant improvement in their performance. This suggests that while ChatGPT can be a powerful tool, it may not be sufficient on its own to address the needs of all learners, especially those requiring more fundamental support and motivation.

This study contributes to the growing body of literature on AI in education by demonstrating the effective use of ChatGPT in improving language skills. It also highlights critical areas for future development, ensuring that AI tools like ChatGPT can more effectively meet the diverse needs of language learners around the world.

Conclusion. In conclusion, using ChatGPT in our speaking classes significantly enhanced students' speaking skills by offering rapid vocabulary acquisition, boosting confidence, providing personalized practice opportunities, delivering immediate feedback, and exposing students to native-like speech. However, challenges such as connectivity issues, difficulties with mispronunciations and errors, long pauses, and varying levels of effectiveness among students highlight the need for a balanced approach that combines technology with traditional teaching methods to support all learners effectively.

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